

Apparent 20-year immunity associated with each *Campylobacter* exposure in humans

W.R. Nelson^{1*}, B. Harris²

¹888 Management Ltd, Christchurch, New Zealand. warrick.nelson@gmail.com

²Canterbury Southern Community Laboratories, Christchurch, New Zealand

Campylobacteriosis is the most common bacterial-caused gastroenteritis worldwide. Its epidemiology is complex. Marked seasonal peaks, largely sporadic incidence, age-band-linked rates of illness, overlain by occasional food-related outbreaks and travel incidence, provide perplexing and enigmatic challenges to better understanding the epidemiology of this ingested pathogen.

*We propose that the initial immune response to the first *Campylobacter* exposure causing infection (clinical or subclinical) in the immune-naïve child generally occurs in the first 1-5 years of human life due to its ubiquitous environmental occurrence, and this exposure confers an approximately 20 year immunity. Vulnerability to clinical infection then increases again as age approaches 20 years from the first infection as the primary immune response wanes. The second infection exposure then induces a secondary immune response which confers a better, longer, almost lifelong immunity.*

*One possible mechanism for this effect is retention of viable *Campylobacter* phagocytosed by mononuclear cells. Another mechanism could be a combination of induced antibody and cellular immunity commonly seen with other exogenous infectious diseases. This is clearly demonstrated by three diminishing age-related peak incidences, each separated by approximately 20 years duration, and each conferring significantly better immunity than the peak before.*

Introduction

Campylobacter species are recognised as the major, worldwide, bacterial cause of gastrointestinal infection with occasional serious additional disease sequelae.⁴⁷ Most cases of campylobacteriosis are sporadic, with some outbreak incidences. Food, in particular poultry products, is commonly believed to be the primary vehicle for infection. There are many reviews of this current understanding of *Campylobacter* epidemiology and pathology.^{1,8} However the direct connection with poultry foods remains tenuous, in spite of the high prevalence of *Campylobacter* contamination in raw products at retail.^{8,26,27,29}

Cases of campylobacteriosis occur, at least in temperate zone countries, on a very distinct seasonal basis, the peak typically occurring during early summer and the nadir through the winter months,^{22,30} but the degree of seasonality varies between years and population age bands.^{14,17,25,29}

Annualised case data, especially in temperate countries, commonly indicate a gradual but erratic increase in clinical case load.¹⁷ Interestingly, both Iceland and New Zealand, with epidemic outbreaks 1997-2000 and 2000-2007 respectively,^{4,5,23,33,41} appear to have reversed this general increasing trend following major poultry production interventions. Similarly, culture compared to serology antibody studies suggest a poultry-associated long-term outbreak in Denmark over the 1993-2001 period when population seroincidence remained static in spite of a 2.5 fold increase in culture-confirmed cases.¹²

Poultry products are an obvious food source for infection and immense resources have been employed to resolve population-level illness by eradicating *Campylobacter* contamination in this food. But clearly there are many other sources as well and we would be wise to explore alternatives.²⁷ We have speculated that contaminated food products

cooked properly could be providing a natural killed whole cell inoculation effect,²⁸ thus providing a mechanism explaining the high prevalence of immunity markers without clinical symptoms. Sub-clinical infectious doses of viable *Campylobacter* could also be occurring concurrently to stimulate an immune response.³⁸

However, notwithstanding some progress and considerable attention, campylobacteriosis remains an enigma. More sampling and more detailed analysis, especially improved genetic techniques, as well as extensive food chain processing interventions, have failed to provide answers of an enduring preventive nature in the general population.

Humoral immunity, a component of the adaptive immune system, is well established in humans as a result of *Campylobacter* challenge. These immune markers are relatively short lived, less than about 2 years.^{2,9,37,40} Continued reduction in clinical symptom expression appears to require repeated and regular exposure.^{2,10,12,15,19,39} However, what is not clear is whether inability to detect these antibodies means the short-term immunity has also degraded. For example, lifetime immunity to hepatitis-B infection occurs post a one-off vaccination series, but the associated antibodies are often no longer detectable within 10 years,⁶ so a less detectable cellular or other immune process must play the major part in this immunity.

Differences in susceptibility to infection within various age bands is commonly noted, at least in temperate countries. Previously noted is the marked differences in seasonal trends within population age-bands, while also noting an approximate 20-year return period in population infection rates.^{25,29} Here, we explore the concept and mechanism of a longer-term immunity effect post exposure.

Hypothesis

Data of various populations, especially in temperate countries, indicates to varying degrees three broadly defined age related peaks in campylobacteriosis incidence. The greatest proportion of illness occurs in those under 5 years old with a very marked drop in illness as a proportion of population until about the age of 15 years (Fig 1). A secondary peak in cases occurs in the 15-30 year age band (20-30 in some

datasets), followed again by a reduction in the following age bands. A third peak, broader and much shallower than before, occurs within the over 50 year age band. This suggests an underlying approximately 20 year cycle in susceptibility, separate from but influenced by the other well-defined infection patterns associated with travel and relatively uncommon outbreak patterns, as well as the strong seasonal summer peak and winter nadir. Conceptually, and mirroring some other well-described infectious disease patterns, there appears to be a strong primary immunity lasting about 20 years, then a further post-exposure boost to immunity with nearly life-long extent which we indicate as a population-level immunity index (Fig 1).

Plausibility

The complexity of underlying cycles of infection and immunity we propose for campylobacteriosis is conceptually not new. What is currently missing is a mechanism for the longer-term immunity cycle since the much less common overwhelming dose aspects (outbreak), different geographically defined strains

(travel), and short term seasonal patterns (summer seasonal exposure and immunity markers) are relatively well described.³⁸ The presence of what appears to be an approximately 20 year cycle in immunity is strongly reminiscent of many other infectious diseases, each with its own immunity-related cycle durations.

Whooping cough (*Bordetella pertussis*) is recognised to exhibit effective, but waning, immunity for up to 20 years following natural infection and up

to 12 years following vaccination.⁴⁶ A 3-5 year population outbreak cycle is common,²⁰ possibly associated with genetic trend changes within the bacterium itself^{24,42} and/or with whole of population immunity dropping below a 'herd protective effect' for this low infectious dose airborne bacterium. In spite of pertussis being a far simpler source attribution (human to human only), the direction of infection, differences between immunity and management of disease between primary or secondary infections, secondary age-related bands of notifications, and even a summer seasonal peak in infections, adds to complexity.^{16,32,48} Pertussis therefore provides an example of a similarly complex and overlapping series of seasonal and age-related immunity changes in a human population.

Quiescence with later eruption, often associated with reduced immunity status, is common in many viral and bacterial infections, such as chicken pox re-emerging as shingles in later years, recurring illness of malaria, or latent TB reinfection. Increasing numbers of endogenous organisms are also being recognised as latent markers of dwindling immunity, such as asymptomatic *Escherichia coli* bacteriuria rates increasing with age, urine being thought of as usually 'sterile' in younger age groups.¹³

Effective immunity via vaccination frequently requires a series of vaccinations (mumps, measles, rubella, HPV, etc), and/or subsequent re-inoculation at specified intervals later in life (influenza, pertussis, etc). As suggested previously,²⁸ we may be similarly inducing a short-term vaccination effect by eating/ingesting *Campylobacter* via many foods, including fruit and vegetable sources, where they are relatively ubiquitous in generally low numbers. Regular low-dose exposure is associated with infection, but generally not acute illness, rather a sub-clinical infection.³⁸ New strains, to which we have not had prior exposure and so no strain-specific immunity, even in low dose, may induce acute illness – thus the increased clinical infection rate in travellers.

There are therefore many examples of illness patterns where post-infective agent exposure induces combined short and longer term immunity markers, with possibly a quiescent phase within the host. We propose that campylobacteriosis population data indicates the presence of all of these features combined.

Mechanism

The annual seasonal pattern of infection is most readily explained by seasonal patterns of infective microbes, although the route to illness is not yet well defined. Rarer *Campylobacter* outbreak incidences relate exclusively to point sources providing an overwhelmingly infectious dose, sufficient to overcome either short or longer term immunity factors. The well-documented increased incidence of campylobacteriosis following travel is also consistent with our induced immunity proposition and readily explained by exposure to different strains of *Campylobacter* when travelling.

The very high rates of infection and illness in the youngest age band (Fig 1) indicates a naïve immune system. Babies may acquire a degree of immunity during pregnancy, but if it exists at all for *Campylobacter*, it is very weak or of short duration.¹⁴ Similarly, newly hatched chicks may demonstrate some immunity through maternal antibodies, although active immune responses only occur on exposure at an older age.^{11,34}

Changes in susceptibility to *Campylobacter* infection are well known to be related to clinical treatments, especially immune-suppressing medications and proton pump inhibitors.²⁸ Many of the events resulting in the need for these medications are also associated with increasing age. This effect could partially explain the broad low increase in reported campylobacteriosis in the over 40 year age cohort. However, this is unlikely to play any significant role in the secondary, young adult cohort.

These patterns are relatively easily explained, if sometimes difficult to attribute directly and accurately.

Peripheral blood mononuclear cells are known to phagocytose *Campylobacter* cells and have subsequently been demonstrated to retain *Campylobacter* DNA, even in apparently now healthy human subjects, a year later.⁴³ Although unable to culture *Campylobacter* from these cells, they speculated that the VBNC state (viable but not culturable via plate culture techniques) could be the reason for a lack of culture from these DNA-positive mononuclear cells. However, this VBNC state is culturable within chicken embryo cells.⁷ Following phagocytosis by mononuclear cells, *Campylobacter* convert to the coccal form, but remain culturable up to seven days following ingestion.¹⁸ Mononuclear cells from blood donors indicated a small proportion failed

to kill phagocytosed *Campylobacter*,⁴⁴ possibly representing a proportion of the population exhibiting longer term *Campylobacter* retention. A demonstrated daily variation in immune response in humans²¹ could provide an answer to why some blood donor cells failed to kill intracellular *Campylobacter*.

In a separate system, *Campylobacter* have been noted to invade epithelial cells, thus potentially resulting in persistent infection.⁴⁵ So far, viability and culture have only been tested within 24 hours of invasion, thus too short a period to affect a 20-year return period.

In a somewhat similar ingestion and survival system, *Acanthamoeba* have been demonstrated to phagocytose *Campylobacter* cells which may subsequently multiply within the amoeba, or at a minimum remain viable. Viable phagocytosed cells have been demonstrated to retain infectivity when ingested by chickens.^{3,35,36} *Campylobacter* have been recorded as actively invading amoebae,³¹ indicating this is not a passive phagocytosis mechanism.

Ingestion and survival, potentially over long periods of time, seem to be possible for *Campylobacter* within various cells of the body. Intracellular multiplication, or a long-term quiescent phase (while not yet demonstrated in humans) seems at least another plausible mechanism to explain the approximately 20-year immunity or re-infection phase. Cryptic retention of viable *Campylobacter* with subsequent break-out on cell apoptosis, may result in an ultra-low dose and thus no clinical symptoms. This then re-initiates immunity markers, while a dwindling re-ingestion and maintenance in a new generation of mononuclear or epithelial cells accounts for the 20-year duration.

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Conclusion

Campylobacteriosis cases at a population level exhibit a number of typical scenarios. By far the majority of cases are classed as sporadic, with no obvious source. For this reason, the well-known high prevalence of *Campylobacter* contamination in poultry meat products, combined with regular consumption, provides a ready explanation. However, this is an overly simplistic view.

Immunity and susceptibility to *Campylobacter* infection show three dominant patterns within campylobacteriosis population data. Occasional incidents associated with specific sources supplying an overwhelming infectious dose (outbreaks), or exposure to novel strains (travel). Thirdly, within the most common sporadic cases, there are the two major time-dependent patterns of an annual increase in cases during the summer months, and an overlying age-of-patient based pattern.

Although the longer-term (approximately 20-year) individual age-related pattern of increase in cases has been noted in many populations, this appears to be the first attempt to ascribe this pattern to similar immunity-patterns of many other infectious diseases. Further, although not confirmed, the known survival of *Campylobacter* intracellularly in human cells provides at least one plausible mechanism for degradation of immunity over a 20-year cycle, as opposed to the 1-2 year cycle reported for specific immunity markers.

Exposure is the main driver of susceptibility to infection and measurable incidence, but infection susceptibility is then greatly moderated by the induced immunity and protection subsequently gained from this exposure. In general, first *Campylobacter* exposure protection lasts for about 20 years, then subsequent exposures provide near lifetime immunity.

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